

**MOTHER'S INTERPRETATION IN THE POETRY OF SADRIDDIN
SALIM BUKHARI**

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Abstract: In this article, the artistic interpretation of the poetry of Sadridin Salim Bukhari, one of the famous representatives of the Bukhara literary movement, and his poems on the theme of the mother are analyzed in detail.

Key words: mother, dream, myth, truth, grief, longing, suffering, spiritual experience.

Sadridin Salim Bukhari entered fiction in his own way, with his own views and unique theme.

Most of the poems of Sadridin Salim Bukhari were written in a unique tradition, concise and popular. He elevated his faith and aspirations to a higher level in his poems. "His language seems to have come out with the words 'Mother' and 'Bukhara'," the poets say.

The image of the mother in the poet's poems cannot be directly compared to any poet's poem. Sadridin Salim Bukhari, like no one else, synchronized his spiritual experiences with his homesickness and suffering.

As an example, we can take his poem "Missing my mother".

MISSING MY MOTHER

If anyone is lost,
will remain a legend
In the bosom of legends
did you go too mom?
If anyone is lost
becomes a stranger

In the bosom of alienation
did you go too mom?

The wind caresses my head
The rain pours down my age,
It is windy and raining
did you visit mom?
You said it's impossible to dream
the time when I reached the Truth
Or as you say
Did you get it, mom?

In this poem, the poet reflected his situation and pains when he lost his closest person, his parent. When something disappears, it either becomes alien to us or a myth. The poet also compares his mother's departure to a myth. The poet is addressing his mother through natural phenomena such as wind and rain.

In the last stanzas of the poet, there are sentences "Or, as you say, have you reached the truth, mother?" The dream of every Muslim is undoubtedly to be worthy of the truth. The poet also expresses that his mother's dream did not become a dream but reached the truth.

Sadriddin Salim Bukhari expressed his love and sincere feelings for his parents through these verses.

Another of his poems is called "Mother's Will".

MY MOTHER'S WILL

Above Saganam
Make a water trough for the birds,
Keep sprinkling every time
Don't be afraid of me.

Because the birds are better than you

Read more from me

Come more than you

Let's talk about it.

In this poem, the poet mentioned how beautiful his mother's will was left to her children before her death. In other words, the mother's request to bring water and grain for the birds on her grave and her request to her children to stay away from me more like the birds are very impressively reflected.

That is, everyone wants to be remembered by someone permanently. It seems that the mother left such an impressive will to her friends, wanting them to remember her more and keep up with her.

The following poem of the poet describes the death of his mother and the spiritual experiences of the poet at that time. As if, in the eyes of the poet, when we give mothers to dust, our mothers turn to dust, and that's why we consider the earth sacred and call it mother earth.

We gave my mother to the ground,
This soil has become my mother.
To embrace as sacred,
This soil is placed like a mother.

Bending down to the ground day and night,
Giving him color, life,
I found out why Zamin
Mother Earth is a human being.

My heart can't stand parting,
I will not go far from the ground...
We gave my mother to the ground,
This soil has become my mother.

Sadriddin Salim Bukhari has won the hearts of readers with his short, concise, and popular words. Sadriddin Salim Bukhari is truly a thoughtful, enthusiastic and cheerful poet. That's why this sincerity shines in all his poems and gives a special freshness.